

ISic0072

I.Sicily inscription 0072

Language

Punic

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Eryx

Place of origin (modern)

Erice

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost, codex of transcription in Palermo bibl. comm.

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644807

Bibliography

Académie des inscriptions et belles-lettres, 1881-1962. Corpus inscriptionum Semiticarum. Paris. At 1.135

Amadasi Guzzo, M.G. 1967. Le iscrizioni fenicie e puniche delle colonie in Occidente. Rome. At Sic.Pun.01

Pellegrini, A. 1891. Studi di epigrafia fenicia. Palermo. At 79-81

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic0072. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4384232>